

RATIONALITY AND TRANSPORTATION OF A TRANSPORT UNIT WHEN TRANSPORTING PERISHABLE GOODS IN REFRIGERATED CONTAINERS

Fayzullaev Gaybullo Oktamovich, asistent,
Tashkent State transport University

ANNOTATION In this thesis, when transporting perishable goods in refrigerated containers, in addition to information about the methods of their proper loading, recommendations for maintaining their quality in good condition and the use of a rational transport unit, information is provided on the preparation and transportation of goods for transportation.

Keywords: maintenance, transportation rules, refrigerated container, perishable goods, cooling technology

АННОТАЦИЯ В этом тезисе, при перевозке скоропортящихся грузов в рефконтейнерах, помимо информации о методах их правильной погрузки, рекомендаций по поддержанию их качества в хорошем состоянии и применению рациональной транспортной единицы, приводится информация о подготовке и транспортировке грузов к перевозке.

Ключевые слова: техническое обслуживание, правила перевозки, рефконтейнер, скоропортящиеся грузы, технология охлаждения

The refrigerated container appeared in the 1960s as an example of the first refrigerated containers. Cooling in them was provided by a central cooling device through a pipe or duct leading to the tank. These refcontainers were called porthole containers.

In the proposed transportation, the appearance of refrigerating devices attached to the front of the isothermal container made it possible to cool the cargo even during transportation by road or rail. This quickly led to the creation of

refrigeration equipment built directly into containers, which made it possible to use containers with combined cooling for transportation. As the name suggests, a container with a built-in cooler has a built-in cooler and requires only a power source to operate. These containers are equally available in different industries, but due to the ease of use, the refrigerated containers quickly meet the standard of transportation along new trade routes. Due to the constant development of refrigeration technologies and the provision of thermal insulation of goods, today refrigerated containers are the most reliable and economical type of cargo transportation that requires temperature control or sensitive to transportation conditions.

On some commercial routes, freezer containers can be used for transportation with the cooling system turned off as an alternative to empty transportation. Intermodal transport operators should be aware of this practice, since the transportation of other types of cargo can lead to damage to equipment, which in turn increases the risk of inefficient operation or subsequent contamination of the cargo.

It should be placed stably to avoid damage during transportation and transportation, but the placement method should also ensure proper air circulation in and around the goods. The wrong choice of container can lead to damage or loss of cargo.

According to the transportation of vegetable products, the sender must make sure that the packaging is strong enough to take into account the risks associated with transportation, which can be divided into the following categories:

- careless handling during loading and unloading of the transport unit;
- compression of overlapping cardboard boxes due to the physical weight of the cargo;
- moisture during transportation that violates the structural integrity of the package.

If the air circulation is insufficient, there is a risk that even if the refrigerant is working properly and the proper level of cooling is provided, the correct temperature will not be maintained throughout the cargo compartment.

Figure 1. The block of rational transportation of perishable goods.

In addition, the accumulation of mature gases can lead to rapid maturation of the cargo, which reduces the shelf life of the cargo and increases the risk of mold and rot. Cooled loads can emit their own heat, so it is important to ensure sufficient air circulation through the packaging.

In refrigerated containers, air enters the cargo compartment from above, which leads to a predominantly horizontal movement of the air flow. Therefore, packages with fresh fruits and vegetables transported in refrigerator trailers should have ventilation holes on the sides so that when assembling the boxes, the corresponding holes form horizontal channels for the movement of air through the cargo mass.

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